

Assessment of Landlord-Tenant Satisfaction with Rented Apartments in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State

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ABSTRACT

This research paper aims to investigate the level of satisfaction of landlords with the tenancy and usage of rented properties by tenants in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study focuses on understanding the factors that influence landlord satisfaction and the potential areas of improvement within the tenant-landlord relationship. Through comprehensive field research employing quantitative primary data collection, this research attempts to shed light on the state of landlord-tenant dynamics within the region. Empirical data through structured questionnaires and interviews were used in this research paper to adequately contribute to the understanding of the challenges faced by landlords and tenants in maintaining a harmonious rental relationship, thereby providing insights for policy reforms and best practices. The recommendations projected from the analysis of data obtained in this research pinpoints common areas of disagreement and breaches while suggesting possible compromise and adherences that can foster a higher level of satisfaction of landlords with tenancy and tenants' usage of rented/leased properties in the selected region.

Keywords: Landlord, Tenant, Lease, Rent, Satisfaction, Property, Maintenance.

1 Introduction

The rental market in South-west Nigeria has experienced significant growth, driven by increasing demand for rented apartments due to affordability (Enevoldsen et al., 2017), convenience (Galster, 2017), and decreased interest in property ownership (Kumar et al., 2022). This trend necessitates investigating usage and satisfaction levels among landlords and tenants. Research shows tenants' satisfaction is influenced by rental cost (Oladipo, 2015), availability (Mukhtar, 2014), quality of basic amenities (Uduku, 2018), landlords' responsiveness to complaints (Bello et al., 2020), and communication dynamics (Kumar et al., 2022). While studies have explored tenants' satisfaction (Galster, 2017; Oladipo, 2015), landlords' experiences remain understudied (Uduku, 2018). Examining landlords' perspectives will enhance communication, improve rental services, and promote a healthy rental market (Kumar et al., 2022). This study addresses the knowledge gap by investigating usage and satisfaction levels among landlords and tenants in South-west Nigeria, providing insights into influential factors and contributing to policy development that enhances rental market quality (Bello et al., 2020).

2 Literature Review

Landlord-tenant relationships have been identified as integral components of housing delivery in Nigeria. Factors Influencing Satisfaction and Usage Level of Landlords and Tenants Studies have shown that several factors affect the satisfaction and usage level of landlords and tenants in Nigeria. One such factor is maintenance and repairs. A study by Babatunde and Afolabi (2018) found that landlords were more satisfied when tenants carried out maintenance on the property, while tenants were more satisfied when landlords carried out repairs promptly.

Another factor that affects the satisfaction and usage level of landlords and tenants is the quality of the housing unit. A study by Kehinde and Obe (2019) found that tenants were more satisfied with rented apartments that were in good condition, while landlords were more satisfied with tenants that maintained the property. The landlord-tenant relationship is also a key factor in satisfaction and usage level. A study by Akingbade et al. (2018) found that tenants who had good relationships with their landlords were more satisfied with their rented apartments. The same study found that landlords who had good relationships with their tenants had lower levels of tenant turnover.

Challenges faced by Landlords and tenants several challenges that landlords and tenants face in Nigeria can affect their satisfaction and usage level. For example, non-payment of rent is a significant challenge for both parties, as it can lead to eviction, disputes, and legal battles. A study by Adeoye and Oluwole (2018) found that non-payment of rent was the most common challenge faced by landlords and tenants in Nigeria. Property damage and tenant turnover are also challenges that can affect the satisfaction and usage level of landlords and tenants. A study by Bamidele et al. (2019) found that landlords were more satisfied when tenants did not cause damage to the property or move out frequently. Tenants, on the other hand, were more satisfied when landlords carried out repairs and did not harass them.

Several factors influence the satisfaction and usage level of landlords and tenants with rented apartments in South-West Nigeria. Maintenance and repairs, quality of housing, and strong landlord-tenant relationships are key factors that affect satisfaction and usage level. Non-payment of rent, property damage, and tenant turnover are challenges that can affect both landlords and tenants, leading to dissatisfaction and lower usage level. Further research is needed to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that influence satisfaction and usage level among landlords and tenants.

2.1 Commercial Housing in Nigeria

This article explores the historical development of the Real Estate industry, highlighting key milestones, challenges, and opportunities that have shaped its trajectory.

2.1.1 The Early Beginnings

The roots of the real estate business in Nigeria can be traced back to the pre-colonial era. Traditional societies practiced land ownership and allocation, al with different systems and customs across regions. With the arrival of colonial powers, land management systems underwent significant changes as the British introduced formal land ownership registration and land tenure systems. Following Nigeria's independence in 1960, rapid urbanization and population growth fuelled the demand for housing and urban infrastructure. The real estate industry began to emerge as developers responded to the rising needs of a burgeoning urban population. The establishment of state housing corporations and government-sponsored housing schemes aimed to address the housing deficit, but the scale of demand outpaced supply.

The 1980s witnessed a significant shift in the real estate landscape as the Nigerian government introduced structural adjustment policies, leading to economic liberalization and privatization. These reforms encouraged private sector participation in real estate development. Private developers began to play a more prominent role in meeting the housing needs of Nigerians, particularly in urban centres. To ensure transparency, professionalism, and consumer protection, the Nigerian government enacted various laws and regulations to govern real estate transactions. The establishment of professional bodies, such as the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV), further contributed to the professionalization of the industry. These developments enhanced the credibility of real estate practitioners and facilitated trust among buyers, sellers, and investors.

Despite its growth, the real estate industry in Nigeria faces several challenges. Limited access to financing, inadequate infrastructure, land use issues, and bureaucratic bottlenecks pose obstacles to development. However, these challenges also present opportunities for innovation and investment. The rising middle class, increasing urbanization, and a growing need for affordable housing create a fertile ground for real estate entrepreneurs and investors to explore untapped markets. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has played a crucial role in the modernization of Nigeria's real estate sector.

International investors bring capital, expertise, and best practices, driving innovation and raising industry standards. Additionally, technological advancements, such as online property portals, mobile applications, and digital property transactions, have transformed the way real estate transactions are conducted, making it more efficient and accessible. The real estate business in Nigeria has come a long way since its inception. From traditional land practices to the modern, dynamic industry we see today, the sector has evolved to meet the changing needs of a growing population. While challenges persist, the real estate industry presents significant opportunities for growth, investment, and socioeconomic development, contributing to Nigeria's overall progress. The oil boom of the 1970s brought substantial wealth to Nigeria, leading to increased urbanization and a surge in property development. The influx of oil revenues created a demand for luxury housing, commercial office spaces, and retail centres. This period saw the rise of affluent neighbourhoods and gated communities, catering to the growing elite class. The Nigerian government has implemented various housing policies aimed at addressing the housing deficit and providing affordable housing options. These policies include the National Housing Fund (NHF) scheme, the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN), and public-private partnerships for mass housing projects. These initiatives have been instrumental in encouraging private sector involvement and expanding access to housing finance for Nigerians.

The introduction of Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) in Nigeria has played a significant role in mobilizing funds for real estate development. REITs provide a platform for small investors to participate in the real estate market, enabling them to invest in income-generating properties such as residential, commercial, and industrial assets. This innovation has contributed to the growth of the real estate industry and increased liquidity in the market. Nigerians living abroad, particularly in Europe and the United States, have played a crucial role in the development of the real estate industry. Remittances from the Nigerian diaspora have been channelled into property investments, contributing to the growth of the sector. Additionally, some diaspora Nigerians have returned to invest in real estate, leveraging their international experience and networks to drive innovation and development. The need for affordable housing in Nigeria remains a significant challenge. To address this issue, various initiatives have been introduced, such as the Federal Integrated Staff Housing (FISH) program, the National Housing Programme (NHP), and social housing schemes by state governments. These initiatives aim to provide decent and affordable housing options for low and middle-income earners, ensuring that housing remains accessible to a broader segment of the population.

Improving market transparency and data availability has been a key focus in recent years. Efforts to establish property registries, improve land administration systems, and promote transparency in real estate transactions have gained momentum. This shift has helped create a more favourable investment environment, providing investors and stakeholders with reliable data and information to make informed decisions. The real estate industry in Nigeria has experienced significant growth and transformation over the years. From government policies to private sector investments, the sector has evolved to meet the changing demands of a growing population. With ongoing efforts to address challenges and capitalize on opportunities, the real estate business in Nigeria continues to contribute to economic development, job creation, and improved living standards.

3 Research Methods

The sampling design for the study was purposive sampling. The study was conducted in some selected cities in South-west Nigeria, and landlords and tenants were selected based on their willingness to participate in the study. Data was collected using questionnaires administered via face-to-face and online surveys. The questionnaires were designed to capture information on demographic characteristics, reasons for renting, rental cost and payment terms, availability and quality of basic amenities, responsiveness and effectiveness of maintenance services, communication and relationship between landlords and tenants, and satisfaction levels of landlords and tenants. Close-ended questions were used in the questionnaire to facilitate quantitative data analysis. The sample size for the study was determined by calculating the minimum sample size required for a population of landlords and tenants in selected cities in South-west Nigeria. A minimum sample size of 200 participants (100 landlords and 100 tenants) were used. The collected data were analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency distribution,

mean, and standard deviation, were computed to summarize the data. The study will adhere to ethical considerations by obtaining informed consent from the participants before the data collection process. The confidentiality of the participants was maintained throughout the study, and the data collected was used solely for research purposes. The limitations of the study included sample bias, data collection bias, and the possibility of social desirability bias in responses.

4 Analysis and Discussion od Results

This section presents basic information detailing the profile of the respondents considered for data collection. The respondents' profile is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Presentation of Respondents' Profile

BUILDING CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENT%
Serviced Apartments	30	15.0
Terrace Houses	110	55.0
Block of Flats	60	30.0
Total	200	100.0
BUILDING TYPE		
Bungalow	140	70.0
2-Storey Building	60	25.0
3-Storey Building	10	5.0
Total	200	100.0
OCCUPANT MARRITAL STATUS		
Married	180	90.0
Single	10	5.0
Others	10	5.0
Total	200	100.0
OCCUPANT EMPLOYMENT STATUS		
Employed	90	45.0
Unemployed	110	55.0
Total	200	100.0
BUILDING SPACE UTILIZATION		
Entire Building	20	10.0
1 Floor	40	20.0
Part of a Floor	130	65.0
Others	10	5.0
Total	190	95.0
System	10	5.0
Total	200	100.0
LOCATION OF SPACE USED		
Entrance Section	70	35.0
Mid-Section	80	40.0
Rear Section	30	15.0
Wing Section	10	5.0
Others	10	5.0

Total	200	100.0
BUILDING DESIGN		
Purpose Built	80	40.0
Adapted	10	5.0
Converted	60	30.0
Mixed-Use	50	25.0
Total	200	100.0
SPACE UTILIZATION		
Residential	80	40.0
Religious	10	5.0
Commercial	60	30.0
Mixed-Use	50	25.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Authors field survey (2023)

From the data obtained as shown in table 1 above; 15% of the properties are serviced apartments, while 55% are terrace houses and the remaining 30% are blocks of flats. The building types are also detailed as 25% of the building type are 2-storey building and 5% are 3-storey building, 70% of the building type are bungalow whereas neither of them are 4-storey building and above.

The findings on building space utilization shows 40% utilizes the entire building, 25% utilizes an entire floor of the structure, about 25% utilizes part of a floor and 5% utilizes other space forms.

Findings also revealed 35% used the entrance section, 40% used the mid-section, 15% used the rear section, 5% used the wing section and 5% uses other space sections. These imply that the mid-section and the space facing the portion of the building that is mostly and easily accessed are used most frequently. The findings on the nature of the building and its design shows that 40% are purpose-built, 5% are adapted, 30% are converted and 25% are mixed-use buildings. Findings on the space functions shows that 40% are residential 5% are religious, 30% are commercial, while 25% were mixed use. For this research, 10 percent of the sample population who made modifications to their rented spaces were considered and the nature of modifications they made as well as its effect on the building also affected the level of satisfaction their landlords reported to have had on their use of space as tenants.

Table 2: Respondents who did modification

HAVE YOU MADE MODIFICATIONS ON THE BUILDING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Yes	20	100.0
No	0	0.0
Total	20	100.0

The number of respondents who carried out various level of modification as shown in Table 2 from the selected sample are 100%.

Table 3: Type of modification(s) carried out

TYPE OF MODIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Decorative	9	45.0
Structural	5	25.0
Both	6	30.0
Nil	0	20.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 3 shows that 45% of the respondents did decorative modifications 25% did structural modification while 30% carried out both decorative and structural modifications.

Table 4: Location of Modifications.

WHERE IS/ARE THE MODIFICATION(S) LOCATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Inside the house	5	25.0
Outside the house	6	30.0
Both	9	45.0
Nil	0	00.0
Total	20	100.0

Tables 4 shows the location of modification made on the building, 25% made modifications on the inside of the space alone, 30% made modifications on the outside alone while 45% made modifications on both the inside of the and outside the space.

Table 5: Part of the building modified

Part of the building modified.		Responses	
		Yes/No	
Interior	Interior ceiling finishes	10 (50%)	10 (50%)
	Interior floor finishes	8 (40%)	12 (60%)
	Interior wall finishes	11 (55%)	9 (45%)
Intermediate	Windows	6 (30%)	14 (70%)
	Interior doors	8 (40%)	12 (60%)
Exterior	Roof	4 (20%)	20 (80%)
	Exterior ceiling finishes	7 (35%)	13 (65%)
	Exterior floor finishes	5 (25)	15 (75%)
	Exterior wall finishes	13 (35%)	7(65%)

Table 5 was used to access the part of the building modified. These reveal building modifications cut across the interior, intermediate and exterior parts of the building. Worthy to note is the roof of the building is the least modified part with about 20% score while the interior wall is the part with the highest level of modification scoring 55%.

Table 6: Satisfaction with Design Modifications

	VS	S	D	VD	Mean	Std. Dev.	rank
Appearance of the exterior space	11	7	2	-	1.5500	.68633	1st
Appearance of the interior space	13	4	3	-	1.5000	.76089	2nd
Level of attention attracted	13	5	1	1	1.5000	.82917	3rd
Level of comfort obtained	13	4	3	-	1.5000	.76081	4th
Level of identity created	13	5	2	-	1.4500	.68633	5th
Level of maintenance required	10	10	-	-	1.5000	.51299	6th
Level of security achieved	8	6	6	-	1.9000	.85224	7th
Quality of beauty achieved	11	7	1	1	1.6000	.82078	8th
Quality of branding generated	14	4	2	-	1.4000	.68056	9th

The above table illustrates the level of satisfaction attained on the various design modification in their ranking and degrees relative to the statistical mean and standard deviation obtained from this study.

Table 7: Major Factors That Results in the Dissatisfaction Of landlords (In the hierarchy of their severity)

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	rank
1. Non-payment of rent	8	4	3	5	2.2500	1.25132	1st
2. Property damage	8	7	2	3	2.0000	1.07606	2nd
3. Illegal activities on the property	11	4	2	3	1.8500	1.13671	3rd
4. Subletting without the landlord's knowledge or approval	7	7	2	4	2.1500	1.13671	4th
5. Breach of lease agreement	9	8	-	3	1.8500	1.03999	5th
6. Difficulties with eviction	6	5	6	3	2.3000	1.08094	6th
7. High tenant turnover	7	5	2	6	2.3500	1.26803	7th
8. Noise disturbances caused by tenants	15	3	-	2	1.4500	.94451	8th
9. Overcrowding of the rental property	4	5	5	6	2.6500	1.13671	9th
10. Unauthorized modifications to the property	1	3	7	9	3.2000	.89445	10th

11. Infestation of pests like rodents and termites	3	4	9	4	2.7000	.97872	11th
12. Abandonment of the property by tenants	6	5	7	2	2.2500	1.01955	12th
13. Harassment or intimidation of the landlord by tenants	6	11	1	2	1.9500	.88704	13th
14. Non-compliance with lease renewal terms	7	4	8	1	2.1500	.98809	14th
15. Unapproved pets on the property	4	4	7	5	2.6500	1.08942	15th
16. Utility bill disputes between landlord and tenant	3	3	13	1	2.6000	.82078	16th
17. Damage to common areas or shared facilities	2	4	12	2	2.7000	.80131	17th
18. Poor hygiene and sanitation practices by tenants	2	6	6	6	2.8000	1.00525	18th

Using spearman ranking and correlation order, the analysis of standard deviation and mean the factors affecting the satisfaction of landlords with tenants and the usage of their rented properties as observed in this study are represented above according to their ranking.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the research on the usage and satisfaction level of landlords and tenants with rented apartments in South-West Nigeria reveals that both groups have varying levels of satisfaction with their living conditions. From the survey conducted, it is apparent that landlords and tenants' express concerns about issues such as maintenance, security, and communication.

6 Recommendation

The study recommends that landlords and property management companies should prioritize addressing the issues identified by tenants, such as timely maintenance and better communication channels. Landlords should also consider implementing security measures to improve the level of security and safety of tenants.

Furthermore, tenant education on their rights and responsibilities in tenancy agreements can help reduce conflicts and increase satisfaction levels. Property management companies should also consider conducting regular surveys to gather feedback from tenants and landlords to improve the quality of services provided. Addressing these concerns would lead to increased satisfaction levels for both landlords and tenants, improve long-term tenancy rates, and promote a higher quality of living in rented apartments in South-West Nigeria.

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